

Language Attitudes Towards Written English Slang Variety in Internet Social Media

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to explore variations in slang English used by social media users and responses using slang English. Social media was the subject of this study such as WhatsApp, Facebook, Instagram and TikTok. A descriptive qualitative method was used in this investigation. The subjects of this research are teenagers or social media/internet users in data collection. The questionnaire approach is the data collection strategy employed in this study, namely by chatting on social media. The questions are based on the questionnaire and carrying out documentation as a complement. In this research, 2 data collection techniques were used, specifically, snowball sampling and purposeful sampling. The data collected was then analyzed based on relevant theories about sociolinguistic studies, and about language attitudes and language variations, especially English slang on social media. The findings in this research show that the English slang most frequently used by respondents on social media is WhatsApp and Instagram. In this case, the slang has four types, namely flippant, imitative, acronym, and clipping. Then the slang English abbreviations that are most widely used on social media are Kepo, DM, Btw, Thx, Otw, Gws, Lol, Pap, Fyi, Guys, and Cod. The reason that makes them interested in using slang on social media is because it is a trend following the times, to make it look cool, not awkward, more familiar with friends, and easy to use among teenagers.

INTRODUCTION

Sociolinguistics discusses language and society, there are variations in the use of language in communicating in everyday life. In accordance with the findings of Suhardianto & Ambalegin (2017) "Sociolinguistics is pertaining to social aspects. The various language varieties employed by society to describe social issues like the use of slang are also discussed in sociolinguistics. This means that in society there are many variations that influence the way speakers speak differently and slang is one of them.

People are impressed by different speaking styles in different social contexts. Social factors will form awareness as a determinant that influences the selection of an appropriate speech style. Sociolinguists research the connections between language and society, according to Holmes (2013). They want to know why we communicate in different ways depending on the social setting. That is, The social context in which someone talks affects when they speak, paying attention to who and where we speak. Kartina and Pangestu (2019) concluded "Sociolinguistics is a science that studies language which has a relationship with society." Sociolinguistics not only studies language but also studies aspects of language used by society.

Holmes (2013) asserts that Word is the smallest unit of language that can stand alone and has meaning. Sociolinguists investigate the relationship between language and society. Word is a critical instrument for interpersonal communication. They use words as they contain ideas in language. A word is a component of language made up of a group of letters or other elements that collectively have a meaning and can be used to construct sentences, phrases, and clauses. The words themselves are classified into four categories, namely nouns, verbs, adjectives, and task words which consist of subjects, predicates, and objects. The next topic is attitude, which plays a significant role in learning any subject, including learning English. One of the many variables that can affect learning success or academic achievement is attitude. In attempts to comprehend, perceive, interpret, perform, or act on an object, attitude is seen to be of utmost importance. According to some experts, attitude is a composite of cognitive, emotional, and conative characteristics. Understanding and experiencing an object depends on these three factors working in concert.

Attitude is a person's attitude towards what is facing him. Everyone has different attitudes and behaviors. Having a good attitude is very important for yourself, as well as for those around you. Attitude is a concept that includes evaluations of people, issues, objects, or events. Attitudes or attitudes can change as a person's experience and knowledge develops. Attitude is the part that has a strong influence on behavior.

In sociolinguistics, language attitudes are a collection of people's beliefs, prejudices, associations, and opinions towards a language. These attitudes cannot always be observed directly so researchers will ask a series of to gauge a person's attitude regarding the use of English slang through a series of questions. When someone has a positive language attitude, they can learn the language more easily and effectively if they want to.

Slang words are informal language created by a certain group. English slang words are not standard and informal. Sometimes slang words seem blunt, funny, loud, or even a little dirty. These slang words are usually spoken by teenagers or certain social groups in everyday conversations. The speakers of these slang words are young people, therefore these words are usually called slang.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Slang is almost always present in every generation of young people. They use slang because the language is easy to accept and understand. They often use this language both directly and indirectly. Such as the language they use on social media or the language they use when chatting with their teenage friends is an indirect use of slang. As stated by Harared (2018) "Slang uses informal words and expressions that are not considered standard in the speaker's language." Most people speak carefully when they are in formal situations, but in many situations it is informal. a more closed speaking style gives a better impression.

Along with advances in technology, the development of slang is also increasingly rapid. Slang English writing can easily be found on social networks such as Facebook, Instagram, WhatsApp, Tiktok and various social media. However, through this research, the author will only discuss slang found on social media, especially on the WhatsApp Facebook, Instagram, and TikTok applications in English Conversation. Public acceptance of the Slang language also varies. Some accept and consider the presence of this language style as a form of creativity, but quite a few also feel disturbed by the presence of this language. For some people, the emergence of this language is a disruption to the language, some communities do not understand slang English. However, the increasing use of slang English on social media is an interesting thing for researchers to conduct this research. Researchers want to know whether in English language group conversations regarding the use of English slang, what types of Slang language are most often used, and how to respond user social media to the written english slang.

METHODOLOGY

(Denzin, 1998). In order to gather data for qualitative research, a number of qualitative inquiry methods are used (e.g., observation, interview, documenting, narrating, publishing text, etc.). Choosing and documenting human activities as they occur in their environment is called observation. When other techniques are ineffective, observation can be used to do research, create detailed descriptions of organizations or events, and gather knowledge that would otherwise be unavailable."

According to John W. Creswell's book *Qualitative Inquiry and Research Design: A Practical Guide*, the researcher will use the case study method and a qualitative approach in this study: *Choosing Among Five Traditions*, that case studies are an investigation into a constrained system or case, or a variety of cases that occasionally occur, using in-depth data collection and involving a

variety of rich information sources. While examples can be investigated by a program, event, activity, or an individual or organization, this bound system is restricted by space and time. In other words, a case study is research in which the researcher investigates a specific phenomenon (case) at a specific time and activity (program, event, process, institution, or social group) and gathers comprehensive and in-depth data over a specific time using a variety of data collection techniques. This study examines topics in the Slang language on social media/internet so that it finds new things in the field by paying attention to observation, interview, and documentation techniques.

Variable of The Research

Linguistic attitudes and variations of slang used by social media users, as in this case, slang has four types of variations, namely Flippant is a fragment of a word to make it easier or simpler to write. imitative, According to Allan & Burridge (2006), slang words included in this type are words that already existed before, but their meaning has expanded and is even very different from the original. Acronym, an abbreviation formed from the initial letters or syllables and pronounced as a word. (Oxford English Dictionary 2020) and clipping, the breaking up of a word to make it easier or simpler to pronounce or write. The influence of slang on social media, as this research found, was that the respondents' reasons were to keep up with the times, to look cool, not feel awkward, and to be trendy.

Data and Data Sources

Data sources in research are subjects from which data can be obtained. Data is also defined as existing reality that functions as source material for compiling an opinion, correct information, and information or material used for reasoning and investigation. So what is meant by the data source in the description above is the research subject to which the data is attached. Data sources can be user language slang in social media. This research uses a questionnaire for the collection the data, then The person who responds to or answers the researcher's written questions is referred to as the respondent, or the data source. Researchers employ observational methods, so the data source is research that observes attitudes towards the use of slang writing on social media, the data source is slang, while the object of research is slang on social media. The accuracy of selecting and determining the type of data source determines the amount of data obtained. Types of data sources, especially in qualitative research, can be classified as follows: a. Resource person (informant), In quantitative research, this data source is called "Respondent", namely the person who provides a "Response" or response to what is requested or determined by researcher. Meanwhile, in qualitative research, the position of the source is very important, not just responding, but also as the owner of the information. Therefore, he is called an informant (a person who provides information, a source of information, a source of data) or also called a subject under study. Because he is also an actor or perpetrator who participates in whether the research is successful or not based on the information given. b. Events Or Activities, Data or information can also be obtained through

observing events or activities related to research problems. From this event or events, researchers can know the process of how something happens more definitely because they witnessed it themselves directly. By observing language attitudes towards various English slang writings on internet social media, researchers can cross-check the verbal information provided by the subjects under study. c. Place or Location, Places or locations related to research targets or problems are also a type of data source. Information about the conditions at the location where the event or activity was carried out can be obtained through the source of the event location. The source location is on social media applications called WhatsApp, Instagram, Facebook, and TikTok. d. Documents or Archives, Documents are written materials or objects related to a particular event or activity. It can be a recording or written document such as a database archive in the form of recorded images of conversations with respondents or slang users. Research data is all the information of someone who is used as a respondent or originating from documents, either in statistical form or in other forms for research purposes. The data used in this research is qualitative, namely a general description of the research object, namely the use of slang on social media. Primary data, Primary data is data that refers to information obtained by hand first by the researcher relating the variable of interest to the specific aims of the study. Primary data sources are individual respondents on the internet/social media which can also be a source of primary data for questionnaires distributed via social media "Primary data is data that comes from original or first sources. This data is not available in compiled form or the form of files. This data must be sought through sources or in technical terms respondents, namely the people we use as research objects or people we use as a means of obtaining information or data. Secondary Data, Secondary data is data that refers to information collected from existing sources. Secondary data sources in this research are notes or documentation of uploads, chats, and comments on social media.

Prosedures of Collecting Data

Using observation, an activity on a process or object to understand knowledge about phenomena based on what has been known before. Which is where researchers observe the attitude of the Slang language on Soial media through online media users. Using the in questionering method, in which the researcher selects a group of friends who can respond to the questions given. Studi documentation, in which researchers take data in the form of pictures as evidence that they have conducted interviews or observations. Researchers choose as many Social media users who can respond. In this research, 2 sampling techniques were used, namely: first, the purposive sampling technique, namely the sampling method used to select subjects based on specific criteria set by the researcher. The second is snowball sampling. Neuman (2003) said the sample in this technique was obtained through a rolling process from one informant to another. The way of taking samples in this study is by looking for samples from the desired population, then from the samples that can be asked to participate to choose the community as a sample

again, and so on. The sample research stage, this research begins with purposive sampling where the researcher chooses a social media user that is friends with the researcher as an informant, in this case can answer the questions and answer question after the initial informant was asked for a response, then the researcher conducts the snowball sampling stage by asking for recommendations from the first informant. Regarding who was asked, the selection of participants was based on who had a media social internet account well it's facebook, whatsapp, instagram, and TikTok.

Technique of Data Analysis

This research data collection technique consists of: Noeng Muhadjir (1998: 104) suggests the notion of analysis data as an effort to systematically search and organize notes from observations, interviews, and others to increase the researcher's understanding of the case under study and present them as findings to others. Meanwhile, to improve this understanding, the analysis needs to be continued by trying to find meaning. In Sugiono (2013) Miles and Huberman (1984), argue that qualitative data analysis activities are carried out in an interactive way and continue until the end when the data is saturated and the activities of the data analysis are data reduction, data display, and conclusion. The data analysis steps are shown as follows:

Data Reduction

Data reduction is a selection process, focusing attention on simplification, abstraction and transformation of raw data that emerges from written notes in the field. This process continues throughout the research, even before the data is actually collected, as can be seen from the research conceptual framework, study problems, and the data collection approach chosen by the researcher. Data Display, Data presentation is an activity when a collection of information arranged, so as to provide the possibility of withdrawal conclusions and taking action. Form of data presentation Qualitative data can be in the form of narrative texts in the form of field notes, matrices, graphs, networks, and charts. These forms combine information that is arranged in a coherent and easily accessible form, making it easier to see what is going on, whether the conclusion is correct or otherwise conduct a re-analysis.

Conclusion Drawing/Verification

Efforts to draw conclusions are carried out by researchers continuously while in the field. From the outset of data collection, the qualitative researcher begins to look for the meaning of things, noting regularities of patterns (in the theoretical record), explanations, possible configurations, causal pathways, and propositions. These conclusions are handled loosely, remain open, and skeptical, but conclusions are already provided. At first it was not clear, but then it became more detailed and firmly rooted.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

English slang is the most widely used by socially willing users social media. This question and answer was conducted with teenagers or Social Media users to find the slang language used by responden in using social media. The results of the questions and answers will be described below: Write down one of the slang language you last used: Based on the results of the question and answer above, it can be concluded that all online media users use a lot of English slang, the most widely used English slang on social media are KEPO, DM, BTW, Thx, OTW, GWS, LOL, PAP, Omg and COD which are where students are more creative and free to express themselves in their social media. Based on the results of the questions and answers above, the reasons that make students interested in using English slang in online media include, among others, because it is trending/viral following the times, to make it look cool, not awkward, more familiar with friends, and easy to use among teenagers. However, there are some students who do not know why they use language slang.

The purpose of this study is to find two points involving research questions. First, this research will describe the English slang that is most widely used in communicating among teenagers using social media. second, knowing the reasons so they are interested in using slang. This study uses 2 instruments to collect data from respondents. Write down one of the slang language you last used? Slang is an ever-expanding collection of informal expressions and words that people use to express their social identity, group cohesiveness, or in response to societal trends or fads. Slang appears to be a part of any language used in everyday interaction by a community large enough and diverse enough to have identifiable subgroups, so the existence of such vocabulary in a language is probably as old as the language itself. (Hudson & Eble). Based on the results of the interviews above, there are several slang languages used by teenagers. The most used slang is KEPO, DM, BTW, Thx, OTW, GWS, LOL, PAP, Omg and COD where students are more creative and free to express themselves in their social media. Why do you use Slang language? The fact is when a person uses slang, he expresses ideas, feelings, attitudes as how he wants to look at the person he is talking to and how he wants those people to see him, to conclude what he is saying/meaning. means that each slang word used by speakers is used for a specific purpose. According to Allan & Burrige (2006), slang has a purpose. To Identify, In order to retain their tight friendship, the speaker addresses the other speaker in slang. According to Allan & Burrige (2006), a young female office worker may protest if a male manager addresses her as "sweetheart" since the social distance between them calls for at least the informal level of formality. She may also find this intimate style offensive.

According to Reveal, Anger Allan & Burrige (2006), the exclamation "Shit!" frequently conveys rage, frustration, or misery. According to Arianti, Suardhana, and Mulyawan's (2018) theory, the speaker uses slang to convey how they feel about something in a negative or unfavorable way. To Establish Intimacy People occasionally use slang terms to express their relationship to

intimacy. According to what Arianti, Suardhana, and Mulyawan (2018) said, The speakers' relationship is indicated by the usage of slang words. According to the hypothesis, the speaker chooses to employ slang terminology over mainstream vocabulary. They frequently employ slang words to convey intimacy since doing so can be a powerful approach to build rapport between individuals. People who have close relationships with others tend to utilize particular word choices when speaking or communicating with them, as opposed to those who have distant relationships. Slang terms are frequently used by speakers to create an intimate atmosphere and make conversation more comfortable. According to Allan & Burridge (2006), there are individuals (regardless of status and social distance from oneself) with whom one is content to (be seen to) become close and to have that closeness symbolized by the employment of a casual or intimate manner. Then, according to Arianti, Suardhana, and Mulyawan (2018), slang words are used by the speakers to make small talk with strangers more comfortable and to reduce social distance. to degrade, According to the idea of Allan & Burridge (2006), these categories are also included in genuine insults that aim to injure, humiliate, and denigrate their targets. According to Saputra (2016), ridiculing someone or something is a common way for speakers to convey their disdain or bad feelings about them. To Start Relaxing Conversations: According to Saputra (2016), starting relaxing conversations is another function. In order to have a casual discourse, speakers will occasionally prefer to utilize slang words rather than conventional terminology. They have a propensity to start casual conversations with slang words in order to communicate effectively in official settings. Someone who is close to another person will frequently use particular words to make the conversation flow more naturally and make them feel more at ease. Based on the results of the questions and answers, the reasons that make students interested in using English slang in online media include, among others, because it is trending/viral following the times, to make it look cool, not awkward, more familiar with friends, and easy to use among teenagers. However, there are some students who do not know why they use language slang.

CONCLUSIONS

This question and answer was carried out for teenagers or Social Media users to find the slang used by teenagers in using social media. Based on the results of the question and answer it can be concluded that all online media users use a lot of English slang, the most used English slang on social media is KEPO, DM, BTW, Thx, OTW, GWS, LOL, PAP, Omg and COD which are where students are more creative and free to express themselves on social. The reason for using slang is actually when someone uses slang, he expresses ideas, feelings, attitudes such as how he wants to see the person he is talking to and how he wants the person to see him, to conclude what he is saying. That is, every slang word uttered by speakers has a certain reason. Based on the results of the question and answer above, the reasons that make students interested in using English slang in online media include that it is trending/viral to keep up

with the times, to make it look cool, not awkward, more familiar with friends, and easy to use among teenagers. However, there are some students who do not know why they use English slang. It has been realized by researchers in the preparation of the thesis above that there are still many errors, deficiencies and far from perfection. However, the researcher really hopes that this research can be useful for me personally and the readers so that future researchers can conduct even better research and develop it.

FURTHER STUDY

This research still has limitations so further research on the topic still needs to be done "Language Attitudes Towards Written English Slang Variety in Internet Social Media."

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